

Personality Prediction using Machine Learning based on Myers-Briggs Type Indicator

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Abstract: Personality is a crucial factor since it distinguishes distinct people from one another. The science of personality prediction is always evolving. Personality prediction using data from social media is a potential strategy because it doesn't require any surveys for users to complete, saving time and strengthening credibility.

Personality knowledge is a fascinating area for scholars to explore. Numerous practical uses for personality prediction may be found nowadays. Social media usage is growing every day. Huge amounts of textual information and visual content are constantly being added to the internet. The current emphasis of research on the standard Twitter dataset. The primary goal is to anticipate a person's personality using various categorization methods. To compare this categorization method, accuracy score is employed.

Keywords: Gaussian Naïve Bayes, Multinomial Naive Bayes, Logistic Regression, Support Vector Classifier and Random Forest.

I. INTRODUCTION

Personality is a crucial characteristic of human beings. Particularly, the study of personality is a subfield of psychology. The components of a person's personality, such as their ideas, feelings, and behaviours, change with time. The study of personality prediction involves classifying people into groups based on their personalities. Numerous psychological tests can provide a variety of personality classifications.

A method for evaluating and identifying a person's personality is the "Myers-Briggs Type Indicator (MBTI)". It defines a person's personality as a group of traits that demonstrate the likelihood of that person's particular behaviours, emotions, and perspectives. Depending on the situation, these qualities may change throughout time. In other words, a person's personality is a combination of the characteristics that define them. Only a handful of the several personality models used today to define personalities include the "Big Five Personality Traits model," "VIA Classification of Character Strengths," "Myers-Briggs Type Indicator (MBTI)" model, and "Jung's Theory of Personality Type models." Since it may be applied in a number of circumstances, the "MBTI" has been proven to be more successful.

Machine learning is frequently used by researchers to predict personality. Machine learning may be used to learn from the past and predict the future; as a result, personality patterns can be discovered. Such a programme is available as a tool for personality evaluation and forecasting in psychology. Businesses and recruiters are putting more of a focus on the creation of machine learning-based personality prediction tools.

Automatic personality prediction via social networks has recently caught the attention of both social science and natural language processing organisations. Individual personality qualities can be studied through social networks. Utilizing a photo, a URL link, or audio are other methods of sharing material on social networking. vs conventional personality tests, which have often been used in counselling, clinical psychology and HR Management. Social media marketing and dating services are two examples of applications of algorithmic personality prediction from social networks.

This study makes use of the "MBTI" dataset and the "Myers-Briggs Type Indicator" to estimate candidates' personality types from the text. The proposed approach applies machine learning to build a classifier that analyses text as input and forecasts the author's "MBTI" personality type. The article is concluded in Section 5, which follows Section 2's discussion of similar studies, Section 3's description of the study methods, and Section 4's presentation of the results and comments.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The Five Factor Model of Personality is detailed in paper [1]. The OCEAN Model is another name for it, and it has acquired a lot of popularity in recent years. The OCEAN Model limits the fundamental components of personality to only five. They are Agreeableness, Extraversion, Neuroticism, and Openness. Market research agencies and advertisers usually employ the OCEAN model to recognize consumers and divide customers into personality types.

In the paper [2], Social media text and picture analysis is done, and the results are utilised to make predictions. Social media usage is growing every day. Massive quantities of textual information and visual content are constantly being added to the internet. The current emphasis of research on the standard Twitter dataset is, Multinomial Naive Bayes, AdaBoost and Linear Discriminate Analysis.

The Myers-Briggs Type Indicator with Text Posting Style is used in the study [3] to forecast personality types. Both traditional and deep learning approaches are used to make predictions in this instance.

In this study [4], both deep learning and traditional machine learning are used to predict personality. Traditional machine learning tests show that the average accuracy of SVM and LDA are not substantially different from one another, with SVM having the high average accuracy in the dataset and LDA having the greatest average accuracy in the manually obtained dataset. The MLP design had the highest average accuracy in the dataset, according to the results of deep learning tests, whereas the LSTM+CNN 1D architectures had the highest average accuracy in the dataset that was manually gathered.

Additionally, resampling techniques, particularly can greatly increase accuracy.

The paper [5] discusses the following. 130 mobile users were studied for their personalities and moods using algorithms depending on signature-based machine learning). For all three classes, a 75% accuracy rate was attained. Thomas et al. (2020) used handwriting to identify personalities, and the mentioned work demonstrated a link between people's financial decisions and personalities. Algorithms include SVM, Decision Tree, KNN, Logistic Regression and Extreme Gradient Boosting.

III. METHODS AND MATERIALS

Myers–Briggs Type Indicator (MBTI)

The abbreviation MBTI stands for Myers-Briggs Type Indicator. This tool is frequently utilised by people to better understand their own interpersonal interactions and communication preferences. Knowing your MBTI type may help you adapt your interpersonal style to fit different situations and target audiences.

The MBTI theory is based on Carl Jung's "Psychological Type" and other publications. To make Carl Gustav Jung's work more intelligible and useful, Isabel Briggs Myers and her mother Katharine Briggs came up with the concept.

Each of the four preference scales in the MBTI has two opposing preferences. The four dimensions of type are these, and they are as follows:

Myers–Briggs personality types:

ESTJ TJ Ambition SJ Discipline Se Experience Te Pragmatism	ESTP Sp Spontaneity Tp Inventiveness Se Experience Te Pragmatism	ESFP Sp Spontaneity Fp Honesty Se Experience Fe Romantic	ESFJ SJ Discipline FJ Kindness Se Experience Fe Romantic
ISTJ SI History TI Accuracy SJ Discipline TJ Ambition	ISTP SI History TI Accuracy Sp Spontaneity Tp Inventiveness	ISFP SI History FI Harmony Sp Spontaneity Fp Honesty	ISFJ SI History FI Harmony SJ Discipline FJ Kindness
INTJ NI Philosophy TI Accuracy NJ Vision TJ Ambition	INTP NI Philosophy TI Accuracy Np Variation Tp Inventiveness	INFP NI Philosophy FI Harmony Np Variation Fp Honesty	INFJ NI Philosophy FI Harmony NJ Vision FJ Kindness
ENTJ Ne Opportunity Te Pragmatism NJ Vision TJ Ambition	ENTP Ne Opportunity Te Pragmatism Np Variation Tp Inventiveness	ENFP Ne Opportunity Fe Romance Np Variation Fp Honesty	ENFJ Ne Opportunity Fe Romance NJ Vision FJ Kindness

The objective of this project is to create a machine learning model that correctly predicts a group of people's personality attributes using the available dataset. It aids recruiters in categorising job applications and streamlines the hiring process. The training and testing data sets are constructed using the internet-downloaded dataset. The majority of the dataset is utilised to train the model, while the remaining portion is used for prediction. The results of the model may be used to create a

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personality prediction model. There are several algorithms used to predict personality, including Support Vector Classifier, Logistic Regression, Gaussian NB, Multinomial NB and Random Forest.

A. Data Collection

Data gathering is an important processes in machine learning workflow. The quality of the data you gather will decide the potential worth and accuracy of your project.

You must carefully choose your sources for data collection and combine their contents into a single dataset. Obtaining open-source data sets, streaming data from Internet of Things sensors, or creating a data lake out of diverse documents, logs, and media are a few examples of how to accomplish this.

B. Data Preparation

Data organising is the process done after data gathering (Data Pre-process). Pre-processing entails putting data in an useable dataset by cleaning, verifying, and preparing it for usage. This may be a rather simple process if you are gathering information from a single source. Before merging data from several sources, it is important to make sure that the data formats are interoperable, the data is equally reliable, and any potential duplicates are removed.

C. Building Datasets

Two datasets for training and testing are created from the processed data at this stage:

- Training dataset— utilised to provide the algorithm with processing instructions. The model categories in this collection are specified using parameters.
- Test dataset— used to assess the accuracy and performance of the models. The goal of this collection is to draw attention to any errors or faulty model training.

D. Choosing Learning algorithm

There is research on the most beneficial learning algorithm. Depending on the kind of data we have and the kind of problem that has to be solved. Algorithms for classification are applied when categorization is the problem and the data has been labelled. Regression algorithms are utilised when there is a need to execute a regression task and the data has labels. Clustering methods are employed when the goal is to form clusters and the data is unstructured.

The below given chart depicts the overview of learning algorithms-

E. Training Model

The model receives training to increase its aptitude. Training dataset and testing dataset are created from the dataset. The proportion between training and testing is either 80/20 or 70/30. The size of the dataset is another factor. For training purposes, training datasets are utilised. The testing purpose makes use of the testing dataset. The learning algorithm is fed a training dataset. Once the learning algorithm establishes, a mapping between the input and the output, is produced by the model.

F. Evaluating Model

The model is assessed to see how effective it is. The testing dataset that was set aside is used to evaluate the model. It enables testing the model against never-before-used training data. To evaluate the performance, metrics including recall, recall accuracy, and precision are employed. In the event that the model is not successful, it is rebuilt using new hyperparameters. By adjusting the hyper parameters, the accuracy may be raised still higher.

G. Prediction

Finally, the created system is put to use in the actual world. Here, machine learning's full worth is seen.

a. Gaussian Naive Bayes

The generative model Naive Bayes is used. (Gaussian) Each class is thought to have a Gaussian distribution according to naive Bayes. Naive Bayes assumes feature independence, which results in diagonal covariance matrices.

b. Multinomial Naive Bayes

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One of the most known Bayesian learning methods in Natural Language Processing is termed as the Multinomial Naive Bayes approach (NLP). The method uses the Bayes theorem to determine a text's tag, like an email or news story. It calculates the likelihood of each tag for a particular sample and then generates the tag with the highest likelihood.

c. Logistic Regression

The statistical analysis technique known as logistic regression forecasts a binary result, such as yes or no, using past observations from a data set. By analysing the correlation between one or more previously existing independent variables, a logistic regression model can predict a dependent data variable.

d. Random Forest Classifier

This classifier was created using a random forest. After numerous decision tree classifiers have been fitted to a variety of dataset sub samples, a random forest is a meta estimator that uses averaging to improve projected accuracy and decrease overfitting.

e. Support Vector Classifier

The linear SVM uses data that can be divided into two groups by a single straight line. This type of data is referred to as linearly separable data, and the classifier utilised is called a Linear SVM classifier.

IV. BUILD MODEL

Machine learning model for predicting personality is constructed using the aforementioned techniques. Jupyter notebook platform. The involved steps are:

1. Importing relevant python packages into the project.

```
In [1]: import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
import nltk
import re
import seaborn as sns
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from sklearn.metrics import roc_curve
from sklearn.metrics import roc_auc_score
from sklearn.feature_extraction.text import TfidfVectorizer
from sklearn.feature_extraction.text import CountVectorizer, TfidfTransformer
from sklearn.metrics import accuracy_score
from sklearn.model_selection import GridSearchCV
```

2. Adding dataset into Jupyter.

```
In [2]: mbti_df=pd.read_csv('mbti_1.csv')
```

```
In [3]: mbti_df.head()
```

Out[3]:

	type	posts
0	INFJ	'http://www.youtube.com/watch?v=qsXHcwe3krw l ...
1	ENTP	'I'm finding the lack of me in these posts ver...
2	INTP	'Good one ____ https://www.youtube.com/wat...
3	INTJ	'Dear INTP, I enjoyed our conversation the o...
4	ENTJ	'You're fired. That's another silly misconce...

3. Information about the dataset:

```
In [5]: mbti_df.info()

<class 'pandas.core.frame.DataFrame'>
RangeIndex: 8675 entries, 0 to 8674
Data columns (total 2 columns):
 #   Column  Non-Null Count  Dtype
---  ---      -
 0   type    8675 non-null   object
 1   posts   8675 non-null   object
dtypes: object(2)
memory usage: 135.7+ KB
```

4. Data Visualization

i) Bar graph showing frequency of different types of personalities:

ii) Pie plot showing different types of personalities:

5. Pre-processing the dataset:

i) converts text in posts to lowercase as it is preferred in NLP

```
In [8]: mbti_df["posts"] = mbti_df["posts"].str.lower()
print(len(mbti_df))

8675
```

ii) Matching URLs and replacing them with 'space':

```
In [9]: for i in range(len(mbti_df)):
post_temp=mbti_df.get_value(i, 'posts')
pattern = re.compile(r'https?://[a-zA-Z0-9.-/]*/[a-zA-Z0-9?=_]*[_0-9.a-zA-Z/-]*')
post_temp= re.sub(pattern, ' ', post_temp)
mbti_df._set_value(i, 'posts',post_temp)
```

iii) Matching numbers and alphanumeric characters and replacing them with 'space':

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```
In [10]: for i in range(len(mbti_df)):
post_temp=mbti_df.get_value(i, 'posts')
pattern = re.compile(r'[0-9]')
post_temp= re.sub(pattern, ' ', post_temp)
pattern = re.compile('\W+')
post_temp= re.sub(pattern, ' ', post_temp)
pattern = re.compile(r'[_+]')
post_temp= re.sub(pattern, ' ', post_temp)
mbti_df._set_value(i, 'posts',post_temp)
```

iv) Matching multiple spaces and replacing them with single 'space':

```
In [11]: for i in range(len(mbti_df)):
post_temp=mbti_df.get_value(i, 'posts')
pattern = re.compile('\s+')
post_temp= re.sub(pattern, ' ', post_temp)
mbti_df._set_value(i, 'posts', post_temp)
```

v) Removing stopwords:

```
In [12]: from nltk.corpus import stopwords
nltk.download('stopwords')

[nltk_data] Downloading package stopwords to
[nltk_data] C:\Users\VACER\AppData\Roaming\nltk_data...
[nltk_data] Package stopwords is already up-to-date!

Out[12]: True

In [13]: remove_words = stopwords.words("english")
for i in range(mbti_df.shape[0]):
post_temp=mbti_df.get_value(i, 'posts')
post_temp=" ".join([w for w in post_temp.split(' ') if w not in remove_words])
mbti_df._set_value(i, 'posts', post_temp)
```

vi) Matches Lemmatizations and switches them to its base root mode:

```
In [14]: from nltk.stem import WordNetLemmatizer
lemmatizer = WordNetLemmatizer()
nltk.download('wordnet')

[nltk_data] Downloading package wordnet to
[nltk_data] C:\Users\VACER\AppData\Roaming\nltk_data...
[nltk_data] Package wordnet is already up-to-date!

Out[14]: True

In [15]: nltk.download('omw-1.4')
for i in range(mbti_df.shape[0]):
post_temp=mbti_df.get_value(i, 'posts')
post_temp=" ".join([lemmatizer.lemmatize(w) for w in post_temp.split(' ')])
mbti_df._set_value(i, 'posts', post_temp)

[nltk_data] Downloading package omw-1.4 to
[nltk_data] C:\Users\VACER\AppData\Roaming\nltk_data...
[nltk_data] Package omw-1.4 is already up-to-date!
```

vii) Creating the training dataset and test dataset:

```
In [17]: from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
train_data,test_data=train_test_split(mbti_df,Test_size=0.2,random_state=42,stratify=mbti_df.type)

In [18]: print(test_data)

      type    posts
7814  INFP  macona depends big family extroverted people ...
2233  ENFJ  blodsmak sveltihel brilliant episode regenera...
7261  INFJ  heylena lol compliment accepted thank jesh f...
7794  INFJ  pac right rocket coffin like packed warhead r...
2950  INTJ  title thread misleading mention world dominat...
...
2006  INTJ  one sentence restrictive accurately portray d...
7137  ISTJ  wanted like odd hybrid dr james wilson house ...
6091  ENTP  took cognitive process test got cognitive proo...
2997  INFJ  get caught fantasy relationship better forget...
5458  ENTJ  doll love movie listed make think tritype one...

[1735 rows x 2 columns]
```

viii) Transform a group of raw documents into a TF-IDF feature matrix:

```
In [19]: vectorizer=TfidfVectorizer( max_features=5000,stop_words='english')
vectorizer.fit(train_data.posts)
train_post=vectorizer.transform(train_data.posts).toarray()
test_post=vectorizer.transform(test_data.posts).toarray()
```

ix) Target values are encoded:

V. RESULTS

Five machine learning techniques were used on the dataset, and the results for each approach somewhat ranged from one another due to the different working conditions of each algorithm. The correctness of the findings was assessed.

```
In [61]: result_df=pd.DataFrame({'Model':['Gaussian NB','Multinomial NB','Random Forest','SVM','Logistic Regression'],  
                               'Accuracy':[accuracy_score(test_target,pred_gnb),accuracy_score(test_target,pred_mnb),accuracy_score(test
```

```
In [62]: print(result_df.sort_values(by = 'Accuracy'))
```

	Model	Accuracy
0	Gaussian NB	0.258790
1	Multinomial NB	0.380403
2	Random Forest	0.527378
4	Logistic Regresssion	0.650144
3	SVM	0.653602

VI. CONCLUSION

As a result, we were able to use social network data and a machine learning algorithm in this study to predict personality. Furthermore, the model for predicting personality based on "MBTI" is a very good machine learning method. This may help school managements to identify personality traits of students by using an implementation of this study.

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